

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DISORDERS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL BEHAVIOR IN STUDENTS AND PSYCHOLOGICAL AND MEDICAL BIOLOGICAL METHODS OF ITS CORRECTION

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Abstract

Psychological behavioral disorders in students (anxiety, depression, addictions, learned helplessness) are caused by stress, academic pressure, and social deprivation. Psychological and pedagogical methods (art therapy, behavioral therapy) and medical and biological approaches (regulation, physical therapy) are main methods used to improve mental health. Modernization in higher education makes mental health of a university student a fundamental challenge for practical clinical psychology and medicine. In this context, the search for innovative conceptual approaches that ensure the effectiveness of interventions in this area is undoubtedly important. The use of appropriate systems of psychocorrectional and medical biological support for educational institutions, ensuring the stability of students' mental health, allows for increased effectiveness of the educational process and improved professional training for future specialists.

Keywords: Disorders, psychological, behavior, student, medical and biological, method, correction, regime, sleep, nutrition, sports, correction.

The development of innovative technologies in the organization of educational and training conditions for the educational environment and the identification of new forms of interaction between subjects of the educational process are necessary for a constructive solution to the problems of psychological and medical biological support for the mental health of students in higher education institutions, as well as the optimization of their psychological adaptation to the educational process. Mental health is a significant factor in students' psychological adaptation to the educational process, as well as their ability to cope with the emotional and stressful situations that arise during academic activities and exams at higher education institutions. Theoretical and empirical research in this area is scarce. It is crucial to recognize the critical role that mental health plays for students. Mental health is defined as a state of internal psychological well-being and the sufficiency of continuous mental activity, which is characterized by the determinism of mental phenomena, a harmonious relationship between the reflection of reality and the individual's attitude toward it, and adequate responses to the surrounding social, mental, and physical conditions of the individual's existence. It ensures faster and more effective psychological adaptation to the conditions of higher education. At this age, the transition from school to university education is a complex adaptive process, the nature of which significantly impacts mental health and the effectiveness of professional training. Furthermore, a high percentage of university students come from rural areas and move to the city for further education. This adds nuance to the adaptive processes and mental health. In such a situation, specialized psychological and medical biological support for students with various mental health needs should play a significant role. Such support will not only ensure the effectiveness of their psychological adaptation but also create constructive conditions for the further development of

personal and professional self-awareness and the development of effective behavioral strategies in various life situations [2; 4].

Students' psychological health is a multifaceted concept, so it is necessary to identify its key components, which are most relevant to higher professional education. This issue is relevant due to the constantly changing demands on the Russian higher education system and its ultimate, ideal, "super-complex" product—a psychologically healthy young person. The knowledge, skills, and abilities students acquire during their university studies remain significant even in the modernization of the education system in our era. Nonetheless, the focus is on helping students acquire the skills and talents necessary to apply this information practically, including in the ever-changing contexts of life and the workplace. A proactive approach to life, a creative approach to solving professional problems, a need for self-knowledge, and a desire for self-realization not only in their profession but also in relationships with others—all these are indicators of psychological health. Therefore, we believe it is important to identify the key areas for maintaining and developing the psychological health of future specialists within the educational environment of a university [1;3].

Modern education should result in the development of competitive, socially responsible, proactive, and competent citizens, which is the foundation for the innovative development of the country's economy and society as a whole. This problem cannot be resolved without implementing student-centered and competency-based, psychological, and medical-biological approaches to student behavior modification, as well as changes in approaches to student adaptation to the university education system [2;4;6].

At this point in its development, psychology has enough knowledge about normal human psychological

development to comprehend not only what causes maladaptive students with abnormally high rates of behavioral inadequacy and neurotic personalities to emerge, but also—and perhaps most importantly—to create a set of psychoprophylactic and corrective measures for higher education institutions that could expedite and optimize students' adaptation processes. For example, incorporating various forms and methods of teaching voluntary and self-regulation techniques into psychology course curricula could be beneficial. This also applies to psychologically challenging situations in university student learning, such as public speaking and oral examinations. To prevent fatigue, monotony, boredom, and mental exhaustion in senior students, it is necessary to infuse the educational process with new forms and methods of teaching that enhance students' interest and energize their work [3;7;9].

Finding strategies to stop and rectify maladaptive processes, as well as researching students' lifestyle, academic achievement, and health, are just a few of the urgent problems that need prompt, thorough scientific analysis to maximize the nation's intellectual potential. One of the "diseases of civilization" is the issue of psychosomatic health, which has been the focus of extensive research for the past century. However, theoretical research has had little practical application. Paradoxically, most people know inexcusably little about their bodies, their structure and functions, or their health, including mental health, as a person's most valuable asset. Due to ignorance, people make many mistakes, sometimes fatal, that could easily be avoided. Human health primarily involves the maintenance and enhancement of both mental and physical qualities, as well as one's capacity to perform effectively [2;8;10]. A healthy lifestyle embodies a generalized and typical pattern of activities in student life, marked by purposeful self-organization, self-discipline, self-regulation, and self-development, all focused on fully realizing individual strengths, talents, and abilities. This lifestyle fosters a sociocultural environment that supports high levels of creativity, productivity, work and social engagement, along with psychological well-being. A healthy lifestyle fosters responsibility for one's own health [4;5].

According to experts conducting research in this area, three main groups of risk factors can be identified that pose a potential risk to students: psychophysical, social, and pedagogical. The following groups of risk factors are distinguished: medical and biological (health groups, hereditary factors, congenital characteristics, mental and physical developmental disorders); socioeconomic (large and single-parent families, teenage parents, unemployed families, families leading an immoral lifestyle; maladjustment to social life: running away, vagrancy, suicide attempts, aggressive behavior, alcohol and drug use); psychological (alienation from the social environment, self-rejection, neurotic reactions, impaired communication with others, emotional instability, failure in activities, failure in social adaptation, difficulties in communication, interaction with peers and teachers); pedagogical (inconsistency between the content of the educational institution's programs and the conditions of students' learning and their psychophysiological characteristics, the pace of mental

development and the pace of learning, the predominance of negative assessments, lack of confidence in activities, lack of interest in learning, and inability to accept positive experiences) [5;9].

Actively addressing psychological behavioral problems in university students may also include such actions as significantly increasing daily fluid intake; improving nutrition; monitoring breathing; exercising and participating in competitive sports.

Mental self-regulation, which promotes the mobilization of psychophysiological capabilities, is also an active means of addressing these problems. Mental self-regulation is a specifically conducted mental activity aimed at correcting one's state. The main types of mental self-regulation include:

- relaxation, which is the conscious neuromuscular relaxation of the body, consisting of maximum contraction and relaxation of a specific area;

- autogenic training, based on the conscious suggestion of feelings of warmth, heaviness, and relief in various organs and areas of the body;

- meditation, which is a method of mental self-regulation using mental actions that help bring the human psyche into a state of deep concentration and self-immersion.

If the impact of psychological problems is significant, primary care measures should be taken:

- Avoid making important decisions unless life-saving is at stake;

- Focus on your breathing (inhale slowly, hold your breath, and exhale slowly);

- Try to count to ten, and then continue working. If the psychological stress occurs indoors, leave the room; wet your forehead and temples with cold water; drink a glass of water; look around; practice calming breathing; act calmly and carefully to avoid falling.

If the stress occurs outdoors, do the following: look around, mentally naming the surroundings; drink some water; practice calming breathing to relieve stress; take a light walk [6;10].

Given the diverse causes of student maladjustment, crisis prevention involves addressing two main, interconnected objectives. The first involves targeted interventions for individuals experiencing psychological crisis, addressing the borderline psychopathological disorders that often arise in this context.

This involves the use of various psychocorrective and/or psychotherapeutic techniques, as well as differentiated psychopharmacotherapy. The second objective involves measures aimed at normalizing the individual's interpersonal relationships with those close to them and, if possible, eliminating the causes of conflict. This requires social interventions, which should involve the university administration and community organizations. Only through such a multifaceted approach can one achieve full rehabilitation in a crisis situation. The primary role in preventing student maladjustment belongs to medical, psychological, and social support offices located in student health centers or university outpatient clinics. Qualified specialists in borderline psychopathology (psychologists, psychotherapists, psychiatrists) provide consultations. Medical and psychological assistance can be obtained anonymously.

If indicated, staff can refer students to a crisis inpatient unit. The work of these offices includes identifying the initial stages of maladjustment, as well as timely prevention and providing medical and social-psychological assistance to rehabilitate students. From the very beginning of training, it is advisable to conduct screening to determine the degree of socialization and adaptation of the individual. Individuals with various forms of deviant behavior, past or present, should be included in a monitoring group, which is subject to dynamic monitoring throughout the course of further training, especially during exam periods [3;6;8].

Psychopharmacotherapy is used for anxiety and depression, as well as for the treatment of severe psychological and behavioral disorders in students. Concurrent psychotherapy is necessary, the strategic goals of which depend on the type of behavioral disturbance, personality characteristics, and clinical structure of the mental disorders. Medical and psychological care for psychological behavioral disorders should be comprehensive, implemented within the framework of a biopsychosocial model of the development of these disorders, and utilized modern psychotechnologies such as neurolinguistic programming, Ericksonian hypnosis, and Gestalt therapy. Furthermore, in some cases, the method of epistemological metaphor was employed.

In conditions of psychological overload, intense mental work, time pressure, and limited physical activity (perhaps due to reluctance or simply laziness), physical education and sports undoubtedly take on a preventative role among students, serving as a means of rehabilitation and restoring an optimal (for a young person) psychophysiological state. Understanding your body, learning to stimulate its activity, and relieving neuromuscular tension and psychoemotional fatigue-this is the goal of restoring a student's physical and psychological well-being. I would like to quote the ancient wisdom: "He who controls himself is the strongest!" Therefore, this briefly described restorative (rehabilitative) method is quite accessible to everyone.

Conclusion:

Psychological intervention for behavioral disorders in students focuses on developing self-regulation, stress reduction, and adaptation, using cognitive behavioral therapy, art therapy, personal growth training, and breathing techniques. The primary focus is on overcoming academic failure, addressing emotional breakdowns, and developing productive behavior skills. Medical and biological methods for student behavior modification are aimed at optimizing the psychophysiological state, increasing adaptation to mental stress,

and preventing stress. The main approaches include physical exercise, breathing exercises, rationalizing the daily routine, spa treatment, and, if necessary, pharmacological support, aimed at improving health and behavior. To address these issues, students are advised to undergo autogenic training, sometimes called psychomuscular training, as it helps relieve neuromuscular tension associated with the restructuring of nervous system regulation. As a rule, autogenic training, or autogenic training, has no contraindications for otherwise healthy individuals. The exceptions are acute mental illnesses and decreased intelligence.

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